

CONTEMPORARY TEACHING OF FINE ARTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the foundations, educational objectives and content of the currently existing concepts of teaching fine arts in primary school. Modern concepts suggest implementing in different ways the main goal of teaching fine arts at school - cultivating an aesthetic attitude to life..

Currently, modern educational institutions are at the stage of modernization and updating the content of education. Today, the main strategic goal of education is to create the basis for sustainable socio-economic and spiritual development of Russia. The spiritual development of a person and the formation of his culture are significantly influenced by art classes, which can serve as a mechanism for the development of the cultural potential of society, its artistic and creative elite. However, the implementation of the main strategic goal of education through art is associated with the need to solve modern problems in the field of culture, which include:

- underestimation in social practice of the role of aesthetic consciousness and artistic culture as influential factors in the dynamic development of society;
- cultural nihilism of a significant part of young people, when the values of high art and their role in culture are questioned or even denied;
- a growing gap between the mass school and high culture, which is becoming increasingly elitist;
- a secondary role assigned to subjects of the artistic and aesthetic cycle in general education at all its levels;
- the spread of paid forms of education, against the backdrop of a low standard of living for the majority of the population, the impossibility of acquiring special tools, modern technical means and materials, which becomes an obstacle to obtaining an education in the field of art for some gifted youth;
- extremely weak material, technical and personnel support for art education, especially within the framework of the general educational process [1].

In accordance with the emerging problems of modernization of education, including art, the need arose for new approaches to teaching in general education institutions. The implementation of the principles and tasks of a modern school requires not only a change in views on the content, forms and methods

of schoolchildren's educational activities, but also a radical transformation of the teacher's activities. The personality of the teacher and his professional training occupy a central place in the system of general and pedagogical education. The relevance of the problem is determined by the fact that without significant changes in the teacher's attitude to pedagogical activity and its components, to himself and to other subjects of this activity, a qualitative update of the school education system will not occur.

The purpose of this study is to determine the role of fine art in the process of spiritual and moral education of the personality of a primary school student. In our opinion, the role of fine art in the modern understanding of the content of education should be determined through solving the following problems:

- identifying the main goal of teaching fine arts at school;
- analysis of modern concepts of teaching fine arts in primary school;
- determination of the conditions for the successful formation of the spiritual world of a junior schoolchild and the tactics of the activity of a fine arts teacher.

As is known, the content of education is social experience, that is, the experience of human activity throughout the history of its development. I. Y. Lerner names four main elements of the content of education: knowledge, methods of activity, experience of creative activity, experience of emotional-value relations [4]. In the modern concept of art education, these four components appear in inextricable unity, but in the reverse order of their significance in the artistic development of the student's personality. Thus, for younger schoolchildren, the most relevant in the process of teaching fine arts is the experience of feelings, experiences, interests, needs; social, moral and spiritual relations. Artistic development in the concept is considered as a path to the humanization of the school. Therefore, the main goal of children's art education is to instill in them an aesthetic attitude towards life. An aesthetic attitude to life is a special personality quality that is necessary for a person's responsible existence in the world. It is expressed in the following abilities:

- directly feel like an integral part of the endless surrounding world;
- see your continuation in the world around you;
- feel a sense of belonging to another person and to human history and culture in general;
- realize the non-utilitarian value of everything in the world;
- realize your responsibility for everything in life, starting with your immediate environment [3].

The development of precisely this quality creates a solid foundation for moral, environmental, patriotic and other traditionally identified types of education. An aesthetic attitude to the world underlies art, human artistic exploration of the world, and can be developed in children in the process of teaching artistic disciplines. Teaching art should begin in kindergarten and continue continuously in secondary schools and universities. At all stages of art education, the pedagogical process should be based on the psychological characteristics of the age of schoolchildren and a differentiated approach to the content of art education. It is important to distinguish between what is necessary for everyone as a factor in the development of personality and worldview, and what is necessary for future professionals.

Primary education in the subject "Fine Arts" is part of the "Art" educational system and provides general art education, which is aimed at the spiritual, moral and aesthetic development of schoolchildren. During the period of primary art education, in the process of

realizing the main goal, that is, nurturing an aesthetic attitude to life, the emphasis in teaching is on the development of: emotional responsiveness in perceiving the world around us; primary forms of artistic imagination; the ability to express an emotional assessment of a phenomenon in sensory images.

The actual creative practice of younger schoolchildren should prevail over the work of perceiving art, which is gradually and steadily expanding. What is common to all types of art should prevail over the specific features of its individual types. In the conditions of variable learning, it is important to note some commonality of the set tasks for studying fine arts. Fine arts in primary school is designed to introduce schoolchildren to the world of plastic arts, the formation of artistic and imaginative thinking, the development of creative abilities, teaching the basics of visual literacy, the formation of practical skills in various types of visual arts, familiarization with the heritage of domestic and world art, and others [5]. Each current program shows with the help of what tasks it is possible to achieve the above-mentioned main goal of teaching fine arts and instilling an aesthetic attitude towards life. It should be noted that, despite the commonality of the stated goals of the "Art" educational system, different authors do not have a common opinion in the conceptual justification of their programs. Therefore, choosing the only program necessary in given specific conditions among existing areas of teaching fine arts at school is a significant problem for a primary school teacher.

To date, several main areas of teaching fine arts have been developed and are in practice. Each of them has its own goals, its own content, its own structure and is implemented through its own program. The first concept of universal graphic literacy is represented by a traditional program operating in many schools across the country. This direction was founded during the formation of the Russian Academy of Arts (the beginning of the 18th century), when the methods and principles of training professional artists in an extremely simplified form were "lowered" into secondary schools for drawing lessons. What was professionally necessary and significant for the training of professional artists was artificially transferred to general education. The modern author of this concept is Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor V. S. Kuzin.

The main objective of the fine arts program is to create an artistic image in various types and genres of fine art using graphic literacy. Visual literacy was filled with new content, coming from the specifics of the artistic and visual language, from the methods of creating an artistic image. Methods of creating an artistic image involve various types of educational activities: images on a plane, in volume (modeling), in the process of working from nature, from memory, from imagination, based on fantasy and imagination, as well as aesthetic perception of the surrounding reality and art. And the specifics of artistic and visual language are studied in the process of solving the following educational problems: shape, proportions, design; color and lighting; space and volume; compositional organization of the image; working with art materials; development of artistic perception and aesthetic responsiveness [3]. The content of the subject is determined here by general topics for a certain year of study, or a certain quarter. For example: 1st grade - "The art of seeing. You and the world around you", 2nd grade - "You and art", 3rd grade - "Art around us", 4th grade - "Every nation is an artist". Communication with art through comprehension of the specifics of its language occurs in various types of artistic activity - visual, decorative, constructive [4]. The content of the subject includes the following sections: basics of artistic representation; ornament in the art of the peoples of the world:

construction and types; folk ornament of Uzbekistan: creative study in the process of depiction; artistic work based on familiarity with folk and decorative arts (the basics of artistic craft).

Each section includes the following types of educational and creative activities: experimentation (exercises-experiments), educational practice (exercises-repetitions, educational tasks), creative works (compositions, variations, improvisations), conversations on art [5]. Artistic and creative visual activity is inextricably intertwined with aesthetic ideas about reality, about activity, about a person and about oneself. Therefore, as a necessary condition, it is preceded by a general aesthetic context (interaction, environment), expressed in the program through concepts, the assimilation of which will help students engage in the creative process through involvement and empathy.

Thus, this subject gives schoolchildren: expansion of their artistic and aesthetic horizons; familiarization with the achievements of world artistic culture in the context of various types of art; mastering visual operations and manipulations using various materials and tools; creation of the simplest artistic images using painting, drawing, graphics, plastic arts; mastering the simplest design and decoration technologies; education of spectator culture. The practical implementation of the subject presupposes the presence of tasks for reflection, for the assimilation of color science and a sense of form, search and experimental orientation, the result of which is collective work that completes each problematic content block.

For example, the integrated subject "Fine arts and artistic work" within the framework of the Elkonin-Davydov system involves solving basic educational problems in accordance with the age of students. In the first year of study, children become acquainted with those types of visual and labor activities that are available to them through technology. The first-grade course is introductory and transitional from preschool classes to school classes, built on the principles of the developmental education system. The content of classes by type of educational and creative work is presented in the following sections: lines - spots - silhouettes, commonality and differences, measure of size and shape, connection by design; sculptural modeling; paints and color; decorative painting; artistic design; architecture and monumental painting; artistic sewing [6]. The content of the second year of study in fine arts and artistic work includes five sections: harmony of color combinations, harmony and expressiveness of color, rhythm in life and in art, symmetry in life and in art, outlines of objects and images. All these sections are interconnected and aimed at a single task: developing in children the ability to see not only individual images and parts of products, but the relationships between them, which is impossible without developing the ability to generalize the perception of color, space, shape of what they depict [7]. The main task of the third year of study is to create conditions for the formation and successful implementation by students of new creative interesting ideas. This task is realized through the study of the following sections of the course: compositional and constructive balance, dynamic and static balance of composition and design, contrasts - analogies, proportions of the image and composition, pen drawing, outlines - shape - proportions of images. At the fourth stage, the main task of teaching is to reconstruct children's already established ideas in such a way that they turn on their spatial imagination about the world around them and the ways of depicting it. Therefore, the content of the training includes such sections as: spatial plans of composition; three-dimensional images; observing and depicting trees; watercolor art; designing three-dimensional forms from flat sheet material;

rhythm in painting, graphics, sculpture; design of volumetric artistic products, our city (village, village) at different times of the year.

An analysis of the tasks and content of Yu. A. Poluyanov's program shows that each method of artistic representation, having been introduced (not passed, not memorized, but introduced into the visual activities of children) at some stage of training, is then constantly included in all subsequent classes, unfolding before students with ever new and richer opportunities. At the same time, when becoming familiar with each of these methods and practicing each of them, children should develop a new and very important ability to look and see.

Thus, the concepts and programs for teaching fine arts at school presented here are diverse and do not equally offer the realization of the main goal of forming an aesthetic attitude to life. Guided by the basic principles of continuous art education in a comprehensive school, a primary school teacher teaching fine arts should focus on the fine arts curriculum that is implemented in the main section of the secondary school.

The development of the modern general education system is determined by such a conceptual position as the inseparability of school and society. Society lives and develops as it learns. However, today, increasingly, politicians, scientists, educators, students and their parents note that the interests of the child and the needs of society are beyond the threshold of the school. Many researchers see the only way out of this situation—drastic changes in school policy towards its democratization and humanization. In this regard, work is underway to rebuild and update the entire education system, a search is underway for ways to develop the school, concepts, projects, programs, and non-traditional forms of education are being developed. The variety of concepts of art education is a striking example of modern trends in the development of the education system and complicates the tasks of a teacher teaching fine arts in primary school when choosing leading principles and methods of education and training. However, any school program in fine arts is focused on the formation of the child's spiritual world, on the development of his aesthetic perception of the world, creative self-expression, and the formation of interest in life through a passion for art.

The role of fine arts in solving general educational problems is clearly defined by the concept of modernization of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period until 2030. When solving the main tasks of spiritual enrichment of younger schoolchildren through introduction to the fine arts, it is important for the teacher how the artistic and pedagogical process will be organized, through what content and forms it will influence the formation of a creative personality. The main principle determining the success of the pedagogical activity of a fine arts teacher should be a careful attitude towards children's creativity and at the same time tactful management of this process. The primary conditions for the successful formation of not only the child's spiritual world, but also his practical skills and visual skills are:

- a variable approach to setting and solving artistic and creative problems;
- nationally oriented training in fine arts;
- stimulating the independence of younger schoolchildren in the choice of artistic materials and means of expression in the process of creating visual images;
- the teacher's desire for pedagogical creativity and improvement of the educational process, etc.

An elementary school fine arts teacher should always remember that changing social values and increasingly rich information flows are always reflected in the fine arts. Only truly spiritual works of art become immortal. Therefore, classical examples of painting, graphics, decorative and applied and folk art should form the basis of the content of the subject area “Art”, since they are not subject to time. Similar processes can be traced in the development of teaching methods. While the most modern teaching methods may gradually become outdated, the methods that the novice teacher has tested in practice and which have repeatedly shown themselves to be successful will form the basis of his teaching activities in the future.

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